

Thermodynamic parameters. The thermodynamic functions, free energy change, ΔF , enthalpy, ΔH and

Heterocyclic N-oxide Adducts of Dioxomolybdenum(VI) Salts

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TABLE 1. FORMATION CONSTANTS

Temp. °C	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	log β ₃
30	4.04	3.87	3.78	11.69
40	4.00	3.81	3.72	11.53
50	3.99	3.80	3.68	11.47

entropy changes, ΔS have been calculated at 30°, utilising Vant Hoff's isotherm for ΔF , graphical solution of Vant Hoff's isobar equation for ΔH and Gibbs Helmholtz equation for ΔS . The first step and the overall functions [ΔF_1 , ΔH_1 , ΔS_1 and ΔF_3 , ΔH_3 and ΔS_3] calculated are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2. THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTION AT 30°

Free energy change K cal/mole		Enthalpy K cal/mole		Entropy cal/degree/mole	
ΔF_1	ΔF_3	ΔH_1	ΔH_3	ΔS_1	ΔS_3
-5.61	-16.24	-1.841	-4.601	+12.43	38.41

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References

1. P. B. CHAKRABORTI and H. N. SHARMA, *Science and Culture*, 1973, **39**, 344.
2. P. B. CHAKRABORTI and H. N. SHARMA, *Science and Culture*, 1974, **40**, 114 and 1974, **40**, 407.
3. P. B. CHAKRABORTI and H. N. SHARMA, *Vijnan Parishad Anusandhan Patrika*, 1974,
4. P. B. CHAKRABORTI and H. N. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 172.
5. M. R. NAIB and C. S. PANDE, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1948, **27A**, 284.
6. (A). CALVIN and WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
(B). J. BJERRUM, "Metal Amine Formation in Aqueous Solutions. P. Haase and Sons., Copenhagen, 1941.
7. L. F. NIMES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 987.
8. HARNED and EMBREE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 1050.

WELL defined stable dioxomolybdenum (VI) complexes are relatively sparse. Though the oxomolybdenum(VI) species mainly occurs as MoO⁴⁺, MoO₂²⁺, MoO₃ and Mo₂O₅²⁺, they are poorly characterised indeed in their complexes as also in simple compounds owing to the complex nature of condensation and polymerisation they undergo, in a wide variety of experimental conditions. However, in recent years some complexes of dioxomolybdenum(VI) ion having compositions MoO₂Cl₂L₂ (L = unidentate ligand, viz., Ph₃PO, PhCOCH₃, PhCHO, THF, CH₃CN, DMSO, HMPA)¹⁻³ and MoO₂Cl₂L' (L' = bidentate ligand, viz., acetylacetone, benzil, etc.)² have been isolated and characterized.

Herein is reported some heterocyclic N-oxide complexes of dioxomolybdenum (VI) chloride and nitrate, the composition, some physical properties and analytical data of which are presented in Table 1.

These complexes are synthesized using MoO₂Cl₂H₂O as a starting material prepared by standard method⁴. The above mentioned easily sublimable compound in solution in dry acetone afforded the chloro complexes by boiling with the acetone solutions of the N-oxides mixed in 1:2 mole ratio with respect to metal and ligand. For isolating the nitrate complex, MoO₂Cl₂H₂O in dry acetonitrile was allowed to undergo substitution and subsequently precipitation reaction with AgNO₃ also taken in dry acetonitrile and precipitated AgCl was filtered off and the filtrate, containing dioxomolybdenum (VI) nitrate was allowed to react with double its mole proportion of 4-nitropyridine N-oxide. Curiously enough, under the same experimental condition pyridine and quinoline N-oxides do not afford any pure isolable product. All of these compounds are insoluble in benzene, light petroleum, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform but very moderately soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetone, and acetonitrile, excepting the nitrate complex which is insoluble in all organic solvents. The chloro com-

Table I

Compound	Colour	M.P. (°C)	Decomposition* temp. (°C)	Percent**				
				C	H	N	Cl	Mo
MoO ₂ Cl ₂ (PyNO)	White	178(d)	150	31.1 (30.9)	2.51 (2.57)	7.26 (7.20)	18.1 (18.2)	24.9 (14.7)
MoO ₂ Cl ₂ (4-NO ₂ PyNO) ₂	White	200(d)	200	24.9 (25.1)	1.69 (1.67)	11.6 (11.7)	14.9 (14.8)	19.6 (20.0)
MoO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ (4-NO ₂ PyNO) ₂	Yellow	190(d)	150	22.8 (22.6)	1.55 (1.50)	15.6 (15.8)	—	18.3 (18.0)
MoO ₂ Cl ₃ (QNO) ₂	Yellow	201(d)	194	44.5 (44.2)	2.84 (2.86)	5.76 (5.73)	14.4 (14.5)	19.5 (19.6)

*obtained from TGA curves; **calculated percentages are given in parentheses.

TABLE 2. N-O STRETCHING FREQUENCIES OF PURE N-OXIDES AND OF THEIR MOLYBDENUM COMPLEXES

Ligands	N-O stretch	Complexes	N-O stretch (cm ⁻¹)	$\Delta\bar{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹)	Ref.
PyNO	1234(s)	MoO ₂ Cl ₂ 2PyNO	1214(s)	20	5, 6
4-NO ₂ PyNO	1275(s) 1286(sh)	MoO ₂ Cl ₂ 2(4-NO ₂ PyNO)	1216(s)	59	6
QNO	1310(s) 1285(s) 1205(sh) 1230[+ ρ (C-H)]	MoO ₂ Cl ₂ 2QNO	1214(s) 1266(m) 1173(s)	—	6, 8

plexes undergo 'base solvolysis' in methanol, the detail mechanism of which would be discussed elsewhere.

The N-O stretching bands of pyridine, 4-nitropyridine and quinoline *N*-oxides undergo a considerable amount of red shift after coordination with the MoO₂²⁺ ion (Table 2). This is, obviously due to the reduction of the O(*p* π) $\rightarrow$ N(*p* π) overlap as a result of the drainage of electron density from oxygen to molybdenum (VI). There is no evidence of any characteristically well defined N-O stretching band in quinoline *N*-oxide in the literature and it has rather been concluded⁶⁻⁸ that $\bar{\nu}$ (N-O) is not a pure vibration in the above *N*-oxide but is coupled with the aromatic ring vibrations of the quinoline ring. That is why so many bands appear in the N-O stretching region even in the pure quinoline *N*-oxide and so no attempt is hereby made to tabulate the $\Delta\bar{\nu}$ in this case.

The N-O inplane bending frequency of the pyridine *N*-oxide⁶ (836 cm⁻¹), 4-nitropyridine *N*-oxide (865 cm⁻¹) and of quinoline *N*-oxide (885 cm⁻¹) remains practically unaltered in the respective complexes. The constancy of this band position may be due to two opposing effects — one similar to that of coordinated water where bending vibration δ (O-H), is shifted to the higher frequency on complexation and the other, lowering in the frequency due to decrease in the π -bond character of the N-O bond.

The Mo = O stretching frequencies of the MoO₂²⁺ group are observed as strong bands at 900 and 930 cm⁻¹ in the PyNO complex, at 905 and 944 cm⁻¹ in the 4-NO₂PyNO complex (chloro) and at 920 and 954 cm⁻¹ in the QNO complex. Since in all these cases both ν_1 and ν_3 are IR active, the MoO₂²⁺ group may have the cis(C_{2v}) configuration in the complexes. A strong band at 1346 cm⁻¹ in the complex MoO₂Cl₂2(4-NO₂PyNO) is due to the aromatic C-NO₂ stretch of the nitro group⁹.

Unfortunately, the i.r. spectra of MoO₂(NO₃)₂2(4-NO₂PyNO) could not be recorded either in Nujol phase or by KBr disc technique. In the former method, the prepared mull reacts with NaCl cell itself and in the latter, there occurs a colour change while preparing the disc and the recorded spectrum is not well resolved and shows no band of coordinated nitrate group but shows only the characteristic band of NO₃⁻ ion. It might be presumed that substitution of NO₃ by Br might have occurred while making the disc. Of course, in this spectrum also, the C (aromatic) -NO₂ stretch and both ν_1 and ν_3 of MoO₂²⁺ group are observable.

The χ^M corr. of the MoO₂²⁺ ion in all the chloro complexes are negative (values range between -95 to -150 $\times 10^{-6}$ e.m.u. mole⁻¹) but in the nitrate complex the said value is 182 $\times 10^{-6}$ e.m.u. mole⁻¹. So, at present no comment can be made whether TIP is essentially exhibited by MoO₂²⁺ ion as presumed by some previous workers^{1,10}.

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References

1. S. M. HORNER and S. Y. TYREE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 122.
2. R. L. KRAÜSS and W. HÜBER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1961, **94**, 2864.
3. A. K. MAJUMDAR, R. G. BHATTACHARYYA and D. C. BERA., *Proc. Chem. Symp.*, 1972, **2**, 121.
4. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 2nd Ed., Wiley Eastern, 1966.
5. D. W. HERLOCKER, R. S. DRAGO and V. I. MEEK, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 2009.
6. H. SHINDO, *Pharm. Bull. Tokyo*, 1958, **6**, 117.
7. J. HAMER and A. MECALUSCO, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, **64**, 473.
8. V. KRISHNAN and C. C. PATEL, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1966, **44**, 972.
9. B. FRANCK, H. HORMANN and S. SCHEIBE, *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, **90**, 330.
10. C. M. FRENCH and J. H. GARSIDE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 2006.

Chemical Examination of the Leaves of *Murraya paniculata*

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FROM the leaves of *Murraya paniculata* the isolation of phebalosin and another coumarin called compound B, C₁₅H₁₆O₄, m.p. 100° was reported by us earlier¹. The isolation of mexoticin from the same plant has also been reported². The present investigation was undertaken with a view to characterizing the compound B.

The IR spectrum of compound B in Nujol mull shows bands at 1255 cm⁻¹ (epoxide ring) and 1725 cm⁻¹ (coumarinic lactone carbonyl), 1605 cm⁻¹ and